

Photocatalytic degradation and intermediates characteristics of chlopyrifos by nano-TiO₂

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Abstract : The photocatalytic degradation and characteristics of corresponding intermediates of pesticide chlopyrifos have been investigated in aqueous solution with TiO₂ as photocatalyst. A series of mixed-solution with different chlopyrifos-TiO₂ ratios were prepared and then illuminated by high pressure mercury lamp. After the reaction for 30 and 60 min, the samples were taken for further analysis. The determination of the concentration of chlopyrifos by HPLC shows the degradation rate of chlopyrifos increases with the increase of initial concentration in lower range (5–20 mg/L) but decreases in higher range (20–80 mg/L). The highest degradation rate is 51.3% after 30 min photocatalytic degradation with the initial concentration of 20 mg/L. Then after the degradation for 60 min, the highest degradation rate reaches 89.0%. Three kinds of intermediates 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinyl ester, 3,5,6-trichloro-Pyr and diethyl phosphite were identified after GC/MS analysis. According to toxicity database, we found that the toxicity of intermediate diethyl phosphate is much less than that of chlopyrifos, and the toxicity of former two intermediates is slightly higher than that of chlopyrifos but could be neglected due to their low concentration in reaction system. The nano-TiO₂ is proved to be an excellent photocatalyst for degradation of chlopyrifos.

Keywords : Titanium dioxide, chlopyrifos, HPLC, GC/MS.

Introduction

Chlopyrifos (IUPA name : *O,O*-diethyl *O*-3,5,6-trichloropyridin-2-pyridyl phosphorothioate), a kind of organophosphorus insecticide that inhibits acetylcholinesterase, has been widely used in worldwide. The insecticidal mechanism of chlopyrifos is to inhibit the acetylcholinesterase of target insects, and the control objects are multiple insects with piercing-sucking and chewing mouthparts. The chlopyrifos made a great contribution to agricultural industry, the residues of which in environment is a big worry. The research of environmental toxicology indicated that the chlopyrifos has potential hazard to ecological environment, which could induce neurologic disorders of organism¹ and has a damaging effect to DNA². In addition, chlopyrifos has a higher acute toxicity and could affect the food safety of human being. To accelerate the degradation of chlopyrifos in environment has become one of important tasks in research fields of pesticide and environmental protection.

At present, the physical method, chemical method and biological method are often used for the degradation of chlopyrifos residues. However, physical degradation is mainly aimed at the surface residues in agricultural byproducts. Chemical degradation has a certain effect for interior residues but a higher cost, and the toxicity of secondary metabolites needs further study. The nano-TiO₂ could generate the photoelectron and electron hole under the irradiation of sunlight or artificial light and then, directly or indirectly degrade the pollutant into nontoxic substances like H₂O, CO₂, etc.³⁻⁶, which provides a new thought and approach for the degradation of pesticide pollution.

In this paper, we studied the degradation character of nano-TiO₂ to chlopyrifos under the irradiation of the high pressure mercury lamp with dominant wavelength as 365 nm, and identified the intermediate product of degradation of chlopyrifos with GC/MS. This work is expected

to provide basis for the degradation of chlopyrifos residues in crops and pesticide wastewater.

Results and discussion

Standard working curve :

A series of chlopyrifos standard solutions with different concentrations of 0.01, 0.1, 1.0, 10, 50, 100, 200 mg/L were prepared with acetonitrile as solvent and then the standard working curve for chlopyrifos concentration-peak area was drawn using the value of HPLC characteristic peak area measured at 290 nm wavelength. It indicated that there is a linear correlativity existed between peak area and chlopyrifos concentration ranged from 0.01 to 200 mg/L and the regression equation was $Y = 22331x + 1346.2$ ($R^2 = 0.9999$).

Influence of initial mass concentration of chlopyrifos on degradation effect :

As indicated in Fig. 1, along with the different initial mass concentration of chlopyrifos, the photocatalytic degradation effects vary immediately. After the reaction for 30 min, the average degradation efficiency was 36.4% for 5 chlopyrifos solutions with different mass concentration, and the maximum efficiency was 51.3% with the

Fig. 1. Effects of initial mass concentration of chlopyrifos on degradation rate.

chlopyrifos solution of 20 mg/L. After 60 min, there was a marked rise for degradation efficiency, where the average degradation efficiency raised to 77.5% and maximum efficiency was up to 89.0%. Between 30 to 60 min in photocatalytic degradation, the degradation efficiency was increased with the increase of mass concentration of chlopyrifos in low concentration range (5~20 mg/L) but decreased in high concentration range (20~80 mg/L). After 30 min degradation, the efficiency of chlopyrifos with initial mass concentration as 20 mg/L was 18.7% higher than that of 80 mg/L, and 23.5% higher after 60 min degradation. The reason may be that the amount of

adsorbed chlopyrifos molecules amplified along with the increase of initial mass concentration. However, the active sites do not increase due to the invariant concentration of TiO_2 , and the surplus chlopyrifos molecules cannot be adsorbed in surface of TiO_2 , when adsorption is almost in saturation as the concentration of TiO_2 is increasing to a certain degree. The degradation efficiency cannot be improved by raising the concentration of chlopyrifos. This phenomenon was consistent with that of the degradation of chloramine phosphorus with nano- TiO_2 as catalyst which studied by Yin *et al.*⁷.

Analysis of degradation products of chlopyrifos :

From the total ion chromatograms of the photocatalytic degradation of chlopyrifos, after 30 min, it can be seen that three kinds of major products (1, 2 and 3) reach their peak earlier than chlopyrifos and the whole content of them is at a lower level (Fig. 2). However, after 60 min, only product 2 can be detected (Fig. 3). Furthermore, after 120 min, products 1, 2 and 3 all cannot be detected and only chlopyrifos was detected (Fig. 4). The mass spectra for chlopyrifos and products 1, 2 and 3 are shown in Fig. 5 to Fig. 8.

Upon comparison with the standard spectrogram in NIST 2005 spectrum library, the degradation products 1, 2 and 3 are identified as *O,O*-diethyl-*O*-(3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridyl)phosphate, diethyl phosphate and 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol, which further affirmed by analysis of the fragment ions. The extracted fragment ions of first-level mass spectrometry are shown in Table 1.

Considering the degradation products of chlopyrifos under different conditions, the generally reported major product are 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol (TCP) and *O,O*-diethyl-*O*-(3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridyl)phosphate (chlopyrifos oxon)⁸⁻¹². Recently, Chitrabalam *et al.*¹³ reported that biodegradation of chlopyrifos by bacterial consortium, the LC-MS spectral analysis showed the presence of metabolites chlopyrifos-oxon and diethyl-phosphorothioate. Zhou *et al.*¹⁴ investigated the reaction mechanism and possible degradation products for the OH-initiated atmospheric oxidation of chlorpyrifos. The theoretical study shows that the dominant products for OH-initiated atmospheric oxidation of chlorpyrifos are chlopyrifos oxon,

Fig. 2. The TIC spectra of photocatalytic degradation of chlopyrifos after 30 min.

Fig. 3. The TIC spectra of photocatalytic degradation of chlopyrifos after 60 min.

SO₂, 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol (TCP) and *O,O*-diethyl phosphorothioate. Zhang *et al.*¹⁵ used γ ray radiation method to degrade chlopyrifos and obtained 4 kinds of main degradation products. Except for TCP and chlopyrifos oxon, there were dithione (*O,O,O,O*-tetraethyl dithiopyrosulfate) and *O,O*-diethyl-*O*-(3,5-dichloro-6-propoxy-2-pyridyl)thiophosphate. Ta *et al.*¹⁶ studied degradation products of chlopyrifos under microwave-assisted electrodeless discharge mercury lamp (MW-EDML) in

aqueous solution and identified 8 kinds of products by LC-MS analysis. Moreover, they pointed out the main photodegradation mechanism of chlopyrifos in aqueous solution and suggested 3 pathways including desulfuration-oxidation, hydrolysis of phosphate ester and dechlorination-hydroxylation process. For desulfuration-oxidation mechanism, the major product is *O,O*-diethyl-*O*-(3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridyl)phosphate. In our research, 3 kinds

Fig. 4. The TIC spectra of photocatalytic degradation of chlopyrifos after 120 min.

Fig. 5. Mass spectrum of chlopyrifos.

Fig. 6. Mass spectrum of degradation compound 1 of chlopyrifos.

Abundance

Fig. 7. Mass spectrum of degradation compound 2 of chlopyrifos.

Abundance

Fig. 8. Mass spectrum of degradation compound 3 of chlopyrifos.

Table 1. Fragments from MS of chlopyrifos and intermediate products

Molecular mass	Retention time (min)	Major fragment informations (m/z)
349	14.640	97, 197, 258, 286, 314, 349
333	14.556	81, 109, 242, 270, 298, 333
197	7.768	72, 107, 134, 169, 197
138	4.122	65, 83, 111

of major products were detected by GC/MS, where the product (1), *O,O*-diethyl-*O*-(3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridyl)-phosphate and 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol are the same

with that obtained in the former work. However, there has not been any report about the product (2) diethyl phosphate.

From the structure of products, it can be said that the degradation mechanism of chlopyrifos is based on desulfuration-oxidation reaction. The P=S bond of chlopyrifos is oxidized into P=O bond and the product (1) is produced, and then the P-O bond conjoints with pyridine ring to produce the product (2) and (3), and finally mineralized into CO₂, H₂O and mineral ions. The possible degradation pathway is shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. Proposed degradation pathway of chlorpyrifos.

The toxicity evaluation for major intermediate products :

Referring to the toxicity library, the LD₅₀ of chlorpyrifos and corresponding three major products are shown in Table 2. There are two major parts in chemical construction of chlorpyrifos : thiophosphate and 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinyl ester. As shown in Table 2, *O,O*-diethyl-*O*-(3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridyl)phosphate is produced only by the substitution of -P=S with -P=O bond in chlorpyrifos. In addition, thiophosphate and phosphate are both the main active structure where phosphate can be generated by thiophosphate through oxidative desulfurization and its toxicity will be enhanced¹⁷, which is in accordance with the reported results. From chemical structure, it can be inferred that two parts constitute (1) those are phosphate and 3,5,6-partially-2-pyridinyl. The cleavage of P-O bond conjoint with pyridine ring, results in the (2) and

Table 2. Toxicity of chlorpyrifos and intermediate products

Serial number	Chlorpyrifos and intermediate products	CAS register number	Toxic records
Standard	 Chlorpyrifos	2921-88-2	Male rat oral LD ₅₀ : 163 mg/kg Female rat oral LD ₅₀ : 135 mg/kg
1	 <i>O,O</i> -Diethyl- <i>O</i> -(3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridyl)phosphate	5598-15-2	Male rat oral LD ₅₀ : 135 mg/kg
2	 Diethyl phosphite	762-04-9	Male rat oral LD ₅₀ : 3900 mg/kg
3	 3,5,6-Trichloro-2-pyridinol	6515-38-4	Male rat oral LD ₅₀ : 130 mg/kg

(3). The toxicity of product (2) is far much than that of standard chlopyrifos with LD₅₀ of 3900 mg/kg, but (3) has a little higher toxicity than standard chlopyrifos with LD₅₀ of 130 mg/kg.

The results showed that the toxicity of *O,O*-diethyl-*O*-(3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridyl)phosphate is slight higher than that of chlopyrifos. The reason may be that the P=S bond of chlopyrifos is substituted with P=O bond of (1) and since the electronegativity of S is less than that of O, (1) is much easily combine with the cholinesterase of insect to accumulate the acetylcholine *in vivo*, which leads to greater toxicity of (1). However, from the total ion chromatogram, it is evident that the concentrations of degradation products are much less than that of chlopyrifos. The degradation products cannot be detected after 120 min.

Experimental

Materials :

The standard chlopyrifos (≥99.3%) was provided by Institute for the Control of Agrochemicals of Hunan Province. Nano-TiO₂ hydrosol (10~20 nm in grain size, anatase) was provided by Panzhihua Iron & Steel Research Institute of Pangang Group.

Main equipments and reagents :

LC-20AT type HPLC was purchased from Shimadzu Corporation, Japan. HP 5975C/7890A type GC/MS was obtained from Agilent Technologies. High pressure mercury lamp with power of 500 W was obtained from Day pulse constant glow source electric appliance Co., Ltd. N-100 type rotary evaporator was purchased from chemical equipment Co., Tokyo. Methyl alcohol was of chromatographic grade. All other reagents utilized were of analytical purity.

Experimental methods :

Photocatalytic degradation :

The TiO₂ hydrosol with concentration of 100 mg/L was prepared by adding water to TiO₂ hydrosol (1000 mg/L). With acetonitrile as solvent, the standard stock solution (1000 mg/L) was prepared by adding a certain quantity of standard chlopyrifos and then the standard work-solutions with concentrations of 5, 10, 20, 40, 80

mg/L were prepared by made the dilution of standard stock solution with acetonitrile. A series of TiO₂-chlopyrifos mixed solutions with different concentrations were prepared, and irradiated under the high pressure mercury lamp. The lamp was turned for about 20 min until the light intensity remains stable. TiO₂-chlopyrifos mixed solution was left in the dark for 1 h and then, put in the thermostatic bath at 25 °C under the irradiation of lamp. The distance between the irradiated solution and the lamp is 30 cm. After the irradiation for 30 and 60 min, the sample solution samples were taken separately and filtered through the 0.22 μm filter membrane. As the mass concentration of chlopyrifos of irradiated solutions was determined by HPLC, the degradation of chlopyrifos can be calculated as by using eq. (1) :

$$X = \frac{C_0 - C_x}{C_0} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

where, X is the degradation percentage of chlopyrifos, C_x (mg/L) is the terminal concentration of the chlopyrifos reaction after irradiated, C₀ (mg/L) is the initial concentration of chlopyrifos.

Analysis of degradation products :

The TiO₂-chlopyrifos mixed solution with the mass concentration of chlopyrifos as 200 mg/L and TiO₂ as 100 mg/L was prepared and then, the photocatalytic degradation experiment was conducted. The sample solutions were taken separately after the reaction for 30, 60, 120 min, and extracted with 10 mL×3 acetonitrile, then the extracted liquor was merged and evaporated to dryness. Little samples remained in the bottom of bottle were dissolved in acetone and then diluted to 5 mL, and filtered. The filtrate was analysed with GC/MS.

HPLC detection conditions :

HPLC analyses were carried out using SPD-20A detector, LC-20AT pump, and Kromasil C18 chromatographic column. The detection wavelength was set as 290 nm, column temperature as 35 °C, mobile phase composed with carbinol and H₂O (90 : 10, v/v), and flow velocity as 1 mL/min. The retention time of chlopyrifos was 7.5 min in this condition.

GC/MS detection conditions :

GC/MS analysis was performed with an Agilent HP-5 MS column (30 m × 0.25 mm×0.25 μm). The oven

program was 1 min at 40 °C, 25 °C/min to 150 °C, 5 °C/min to 250 °C and 10 °C/min to 280 °C (10 min). The vaporizer temperature was set at 280 °C, ion source temperature at 230 °C, and quadrupole rods temperature at 150 °C. EI ion source was used and the electron energy was set as 70 eV. The mass range was 50 ~ 550 μ m, the carrier gas was helium, and the flow velocity was set at 1.2 mL/min. The samples (1 μ L) were injected to GC/MS splitlessly and the lag time for solvent was 3 min.

Conclusions :

Under the irradiation of high pressure mercury lamp and with nano-TiO₂ as photocatalyst, the degradation efficiency of chlopyrifos increased with the increase of concentration of chlopyrifos in low concentration range (5 ~ 20 mg/L) but decreased in high concentration range (20 ~ 80 mg/L). After 30 min degradation, the maximum degradation efficiency was 51.3% with initial concentration as 20 mg/L. After 60 min, the maximum efficiency significantly increased to 89.0%. Three kinds of degradation intermediate products *O,O*-diethyl-*O*-(3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridyl)phosphate, diethyl phosphite and 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol were detected by GC/MS. According to the structural characteristics of degradation products, the probable degradation mechanism is prepared. Referring to the toxicity library, the toxicity of intermediate product (2) is much less than chlopyrifos in toxicity. The toxicity of (3) is slightly higher than that of chlopyrifos. However, the intermediate products are of lower concentration in reaction system and then further degraded thoroughly which cannot be detected after photocatalytic degradation for 120 min. So the toxicity of intermediates could be neglected for the whole reaction system. The degradation of chlopyrifos with nano-TiO₂ as photocatalyst has the advantages of good speed, good efficiency, and low toxicity, which provides a potential technique for degradation of chlopyrifos and/or other kinds of organic pollutant.

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References

1. T. A. Slotkin, F. J. Seidler, C. Wu, E. A. MacKillop and K. G. Linden. *Environ. Health Persp.*, 2009, **117**, 338.
2. S. C. Gupta, M. Mishra, A. Sharma, T. G. R. D. Balaji. R. Kumar, R. K. Mishra and D. K. Chowdhuri. *Ecotox. Environ. Safe*, 2010, **73**, 1415.
3. N. Philippidis, S. Sotiropoulos, A. Efsthathiou and I. Poullos, *J. Photochem. Photobiol A : Chem.*, 2009, **204**, 129.
4. G. R. M. Echavia, F. Matzusawab and N. Negishi, *Chemosphere*, 2009, **76**, 595.
5. M. V. P. Sharma, G. Sadanandam, A. Ratnamala, V. D. Kumari and M. Subrahmanyam, *J. Hazardous Materials*, 2009, **171**, 626.
6. L. Lhomme, S. Brosillon and D. Wolbert, *Chemosphere*, 2008, **70**, 381.
7. L. Yin, J. Zhu, L. Wen, S. Yang and Q. Xie, *J. Central South Univ. Sci. Tech.*, 2009, **40**, 139.
8. M. K. Morgana, L. S. Sheldona, C. W. Croghana, P. A. Jones, G. L. Robertson, J. C. Chuang, N. K. Wilson and C. W. Lu, *J. Expo. Anal. Env. Epid.*, 2005, **15**, 297.
9. T. Cáceres, W. He, R. Naidu and M. Megharaj, *Water Res.*, 2007, **41**, 4497.
10. S. Anwar, F. Liaquat, Q. M. Khan, Z. M. Khalid and S. Iqbal, *J. Hazardous Materials*, 2009, **168**, 400.
11. K. Maya, R. S. Singh, S. N. Upadhyay and S. K. Dubey, *Process Biochem.*, 2011, **46**, 2130.
12. Y. Zhang, Y. Hou, F. Chen, Z. Xiao, J. Zhang and X. Hu, *Chemosphere*, 2011, **82**, 1109.
13. C. Sasikala, S. Jiwal, P. Rout and M. Ramya, *World J. Microb. Biot.*, 2012, **28**, 1301.
14. Q. Zhou, X. Sun, R. Gao, Q. Zhang and W. Wang, *J. Mol. Struc-Theochem.*, 2010, **952**, 8.
15. Q. Zhang, F. Wang and Y. Ha, *Sci. Agr. Sin.*, 2010, **43**, 1041.
16. N. Ta and C. Sun, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2011, **34**, 8.
17. C. Slegers and B. Tilquin, *Radiat. Phys. Chem.*, 2006, **75**, 1006.